

Annual Report

2021

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Preface

Early in 2021, we submitted our new funding application to the Swedish Research Council for the 2023–2026 period. The process to formulate our vision and operations for the coming years began in 2020 and involved many colleagues from the consortium universities and network members, as well as our Steering Committee and Grand Annual General Meeting, who are the governing bodies of SND. This was an inspiring and fruitful discussion on how to renew and develop SND. The application scored very high in the peer review and the Swedish Research Council approved it without any major changes. This will give SND a valuable stability over the coming years as we implement the outlined activities and operations.

In parallel to the internal development of SND, an inquiry on how to improve research data management on a national level was presented during the year. The commission of inquiry was appointed by the Swedish government and led by the former minister of research and higher education, Tobias Krantz. SND was, together with a handful of other infrastructures, pointed out as being of central importance to providing Swedish researchers with a competitive research data environment within the new era of Open Science. In short, the commission proposed a new research data authority that would be able to also manage sensitive data for other authorities, e.g. higher education institutions. This is a construction similar to what already exists in

Finland and Norway. However, the creation of this new authority, if it becomes a reality, is expected to take several years. Hopefully we will know the answer before our current funding period ends in 2022. In the meantime, we are well on our way to creating a functioning model for managing sensitive data within the SND network. Local storage solutions with connections to our systems are being set up at several network members, and SND's legal network has produced a guide to support the process of managing requests to access sensitive data.

As you will see in this annual report, SND continues to grow in terms of outgoing as well as incoming research data. Our digital tools and services have developed during the year with improved usability, and thanks to new working modalities we have had more workshops and training sessions in Open Data than ever, despite the pandemic. Internationally our work also continued to develop even though we could not physically travel, and our relation as a member of the European Open Science Cloud has matured after the establishment of the EOSC Association.

It can only get even better once we get out of the pandemic!

*Max Petzold,
Director of SND*

SND Network and Consortium

As the pandemic continued in 2021, all our network activities had to be held as virtual webinars. The SND main office has had primary responsibility, but some events were organised in cooperation with domain specialists and members of the SND network. As a national RDA node, SND also co-organised two RDA events.

The following network events were organised as webinars:

25 JAN + 24 MAY

Meeting for the SND IT forum

The SND IT forum is an opportunity for IT experts connected to the DAU operations and other research data related activities in the SND network to meet and discuss current problems and possible solutions.

28 JAN

Personal information in research data – how do we manage it in practice?

SND legal officer Erica Schweder presented the current efforts to increase knowledge of and improve the routines for how to manage and share personal data from a legal point of view.

10 FEB + 10 MAY + 8 SEPT + 1 DEC

National collaboration on enterprise architecture and research data

A series of recurring meetings on a national level to collaborate on issues in enterprise architecture and research data.

3–4 MARCH

Webinar on API for indexing research data

An event held in collaboration with Sunet and SNIC to introduce and discuss their common API that has been developed for indexing research data. The API connects the SND system DORIS to the storage solutions at the Swedish HEIs and makes it possible to make research data accessible without having them leave the HEI.

10 MARCH

What's new from 2023: SND's grants application to the Swedish Research Council

A presentation of the contents in SND's application for funding from the Swedish Research Council for the 2023–2026 period. What will change at SND and which initiatives are we planning?

15 APRIL + 6 MAY

Two steps towards open data 2026

Two webinars that addressed the government's goal that publicly funded data should be made accessible and "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" no later than 2026. The first webinar focused on researchers and research support, with presentations from different representatives. In the second webinar representatives from larger Swedish research funders gave their perspectives and suggestions on how to achieve the goal.

26 MAY

Legal perspectives – open access to research data

SND legal officer Erica Schweder explained the applicable frameworks in administrative legislation and what issues that need to be managed when research data shall be made openly accessible.

7 JUNE

What can we learn from one another?

This webinar provided an opportunity to listen to and learn from other network members, and to discuss shared experiences from the DAU work.

30 AUG

RDA webinar: How to make software FAIR

An event in collaboration with the Danish RDA node, operated by DeIC. The focus of this webinar was on the basic differences between data and software, related to the FAIR principles.

22 SEPT

Data management plans – how do we offer researchers good support?

An opportunity to learn from Karolinska Institutet and their experiences from reviewing data management plans. Participants discussed their experiences from DMP related work, and how they can support and learn from one another.

20 OCT

Research data policies – experiences and discussion

This webinar focused on experiences from creating research data policies or similar documents at the HEIs. Some of the SND network members gave presentations about what has been done and what is being done in their organisations.

5 NOV

RDA webinar: Standards and best practice recommendations for software repositories

An RDA event focused on what needs to be done in regard to sharing and reusing software, and how to give software a persistent identifier that lives up to the needs of software seen as a living digital object.

17 NOV

This is how we do it – building functioning support for research data management

Here we highlighted experiences from some of the HEIs that have come a long way in their establishment of research data support functions. There were discussions on how to build a well-functioning DAU, including common denominators for successful units, such as staff categories, mandates, and resources.

16 DEC

Open access to research data – research support, managing personal data, and data disclosure

A webinar about open access to research data and how researchers can be supported in their work with managing and disclosing data that contain personal information.

SND has also organised webinars to provide support in how to review data and metadata, and drop-in sessions on SND related issues such as terminology, DORIS, and IT.

Following up with the SND Network Data Access Units

Just like the previous year, SND director Max Petzold and deputy director Elisabeth Strandhagen held a series of meetings with the DAUs (Data Access Unit) in the SND network during spring. Represented in the meetings was also the SND contact for the respective DAU. These meetings are important and informative and will continue to be held regularly. They provide a useful insight into the current work in the DAU and an opportunity for both parties to raise questions and ideas.

A New DAU Support Group

In spring, 2021, SND decided that the support offered to the Data Access Units in Swedish HEIs should enter a new phase from September 2021. The previous solution with a dedicated contact person for each HEI from the SND main office was replaced with a common DAU support group. The purpose of this change was partly to provide the DAUs with unified support, partly to give the group a mandate to be proactive in certain matters. The DAU support group will have better opportunity to gain an overview of recurring questions among the DAUs, which will make it possible to bring HEIs together for common development and solutions.

DAU staff can contact the support group with questions concerning how to start and establish a DAU, work processes, coordination with their organisations, and collaborations between DAUs or with the SND main office. The group can be a sounding board in matters of storage, data management (apart from data reviews), and data management plans. During the year, the group has met with several DAUs. They have also created supporting documents based on DAU activities and their various needs, work which will continue.

The DAU Council

The DAU Council consists of one member from each of the nine consortium universities and two representatives from the SND main office. The purpose is to strengthen the collaboration within the SND consortium and to be a link between the SND Steering Committee and the various national activities. During the year, the council introduced monthly meetings.

The Domain Specialists

The domain specialists are experts in various scientific fields or in areas of research data management. They currently cover the social sciences, humanities, public health and epidemiology, environmental data, sensitive data, spatial data (geodata and GIS data), materials science, life science, registry-based medical and other research, as well as interdisciplinary population-based research related to registries and biobanks. The domain specialists contribute with expertise at both local and national levels.

New Regulatory Documents

During 2021, the SND Steering Committee has adopted two new policies: the *SND Policy for Authorisation Management* and the *SND Policy for Review of Data and Metadata*. The *SND Policy for Persistent Identifiers (PID) on Research Data* has also been revised.

Members of the SND Network

At the end of 2021, the SND Network consisted of 35 members. Consortium members in bold text.

Internal Projects

During 2021, SND has continued to develop and improve the services offered. New features have been added to the system DORIS to increase its usability. The storage solution created in collaboration with Sunet, which will enable sharing of data that contain personal information in the SND catalogue, has been taken into active use.

New Features in DORIS

The development of DORIS, SND's Data Organisation and Information System, is ongoing. At the end of the year, the work was changed from a project to being a part of the everyday operations at SND. The development phase has been intense and involved staff from several sections at the SND main office. Reference groups, consisting of domain specialists/researchers and DAU staff, have played an important role in the work.

Apart from updates to the user interface, the following larger development efforts have been made during 2021:

- A new feature for managing data requests
- A new notes function for documentation during the review process
- Additional metadata profiles
- Enhanced administrative interface
- Support for issuing organisation-specific DOI prefixes
- Improved support for harvesting metadata to and from the SND catalogue via OAI-PMH

- Implementation of ORCID login
- Implementation of BagIt for the data flow processes in SND CARE

Additional Metadata Profiles and a Function for Registering Data

Since 2019, SND has had several metadata profiles that are specific for various research areas to describe data that will be made accessible through the SND research data catalogue. In 2021, two additional profiles were added: Natural Sciences and Engineering and Technology. SND aims to develop specific profiles for the top classification levels in the OECD classification [Fields of Research and Development \(FORD\)](#). During the year we have also reviewed and updated the existing metadata profiles.

As a complement to the regular data descriptions that can be created in DORIS, we have introduced a possibility to register data in the system. The organisations in the SND network that manage locally stored data can choose to provide their researchers with this service. To register data, as opposed to describing data, requires fewer metadata fields and has a more limited review process. A registered catalogue entry is findable in the SND catalogue but has lower compliance with the [FAIR principles](#).

Improving the Digital Accessibility of the Website

During the year, the SND website has been adapted to the legal requirements for digital accessibility that public organisations are obligated to follow, as stated in the *Act on the Accessibility of Digital Public Services*. This means that several actions have been taken to make the website accessible for as many people as possible. The work is ongoing, and the goal is to live up to the requirements for digital accessibility on an AA level in the [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines](#), version 2.1.

Guides to Managing Personal Data

As the number of submissions of data descriptions to the SND research data catalogue increases, we also receive more requests to make studies with datasets that contain personal data accessible. Before SND can make these studies accessible, the responsible HEI must have a local storage solution, as well as staff who can manage both reviews and disclosure of the data. For that purpose, we have produced guides to managing personal data*. In the *“Guide to disclosing research data that contain personal data”* you find information about what you need to consider before data can be disclosed, and in the *“Guide to assessing personal data when reviewing datasets”* you learn more about the review process.

In addition to these two guides, a workshop has been held for research data advisors at the SND main office and a webinar titled *“Personal information in research data – how do we manage it in practice”* has been arranged for the SND network.

**The work was initiated in 2021 and the documents will be finalised and made available during 2022.*

Collaboration with Sunet on Storage Solutions

The collaboration with Sunet regarding API development and storage has continued with further development of the service. The first users have begun to actively use the integration between the Sunet storage service and SND’s system DORIS for making data that are stored with Sunet accessible through SND. Simultaneously, we have identified a need to develop a new integration between DORIS and Sunet’s new service Sunet Drive, and several HEIs are waiting to make their data accessible through DORIS until this integration has been implemented. Due to a lack of system developers with adequate skills, the development has been delayed and is now planned for the first part of 2022.

There have been discussions during the year about how to divide responsibilities between SND and Sunet, and the parties have agreed on which services each organisation shall have responsibility for. As a consequence, some services will transfer from Sunet to SND for long-term administration and development.

In 2021, SND has established a working group with the IT architecture network ATI. This group will monitor the entirety of data and metadata flows in the HEIs, as well as the process for making data accessible through SND. They will also investigate the best ways to integrate the services that SND develop with the HEIs’ workflows and administration models.

International Cooperation

SND is part of a global infrastructure, where collaboration plays a central part. SND's collaborations fall into two main categories: initiatives from the European Union, such as EOSC and CESSDA ERIC, and various organisations that provide essential services or expertise related to data management and repositories.

EOSC

In 2015, the European Commission initiated the process to create the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#), with the objective to federate existing research data infrastructures in Europe and realise a web of FAIR data and related services for science.

[The EOSC Association](#) is the legal entity established to govern EOSC. It was formed in July 2020 with four founding members and has since grown to over 200 members and observers. SND, with the University of Gothenburg as host university, is a member, as well as six other Swedish organisations, five of which are SND consortium universities.

The Association members are jointly responsible for delivering the objectives agreed in the *Memorandum of Understanding*, signed by the European Union and EOSC Association to form the official partnership. The EOSC ecosystem is being co-created in a series of funded

projects and initiatives from member states and associated countries.

CESSDA

[The Consortium of European Social Science Data](#)

[Archives \(CESSDA\)](#) has a mission to provide a full-scale, sustainable research infrastructure that enables the research community to conduct high-quality research in the social sciences. The goal is to create a consortium of certified trusted data repositories with full European coverage. CESSDA is part of the creation of EOSC, and actively supports the implementation of the FAIR data principles.

During 2021, Italy was accepted as new member country, and the total number of members added up to 22 plus one observer. Each member country has a designated Service Provider (SP) that meets specific demands and requirements of CESSDA. SND is the appointed Swedish SP. The CESSDA work is coordinated from the main office in Bergen, Norway, but the main share of the CESSDA operations is based on the decentralised services that are provided by the member countries' SPs.

In 2021, CESSDA introduced a new strategic way of working, implementing two-year roadmaps. Agenda 21–22 includes eleven tasks to complete during the period. Two of them are led by SND: *Widening of CESSDA European Coverage* and *Trust Activities*. SND is also involved in *Journals Outreach*, *Data Archiving Guide (DAG)*, and *CESSDA Resource Directory*.

SND is appointed Content Contact for the upcoming European Question Bank (EQB) and is also a part of the Technical Committee as a non-executive Contact. Furthermore, SND is responsible for the Swedish language translations of the multilingual ELSST thesaurus and the common controlled vocabularies in CESSDA.

RDA/RDA Sweden

The [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#) is driven by its more than 12,000 members. On the RDA platform researchers and other research data experts meet to exchange and develop ideas and technology, as well as tools for data sharing, data management, certification of data repositories, and education and training.

In June 2019, Sweden was one of six countries selected as new RDA Europe nodes. SND coordinates [the Swedish node](#) and drives the RDA node work in Sweden. The purpose of the work is to promote best practices in research data management and to strive to increase the awareness of RDA and research data-related questions in Sweden. In 2021, two webinars organised by the Swedish and Danish RDA nodes were held: *How to make software FAIR*, and *Standards and best practice recommendations for software repositories*. SND staff, researchers, and research data experts in the SND network contribute to the development of RDA as individual members. Several of them are involved in various interest and working groups.

Other International Cooperation

The participation in international organisations in the fields of metadata standards and persistent identifiers has continued through the memberships in the [DDI \(Data Documentation Initiative\) Alliance](#) and [DataCite](#). In 2021, SND extended its work with persistent identifiers by taking over SNIC's membership in [ePIC](#). ePIC is a consortium of European partners that provide PID services for the European Research Community, based on the handle system.

SND staff has also been represented in the [CoreTrust-Seal](#) Assembly of Reviewers. The Swedish membership in the [Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research \(ICPSR\)](#) is administered by SND. Other international memberships are the [International Federation of Data Organisations \(IFDO\)](#) and the [World Data System \(WDS\)](#).

Due to the pandemic the IASSIST conference, hosted by SND and originally planned to take place in Gothenburg in May 2020, was postponed several times. The current plan is to arrange a hybrid event in June 2022.

Projects

In 2021, SND continued its participation in three infrastructure projects funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Programme. SND also took part in one Cost Action project.

[ARIADNEplus](#) is the extension of the previous ARIADNE project (2013–2017), which brought together and integrated existing archaeological data infrastructures in Europe. In both projects, SND has provided expertise and contributed to the creation of the project portal, the development of standards, best practices, controlled vocabularies, and the building of networks of experts, hereby making national and international research data FAIR.

SND participates in ten Work Packages as a content provider, technical partner, and a national coordinator. SND is also leader for the WP *Innovative Services for Users* and member of the Steering Committee. The project started in January 2019 and runs for 48 months.

[EOSC-Nordic](#) aims to facilitate the coordination of initiatives relevant to EOSC within the Nordic and Baltic countries. The goal is to exploit synergies to achieve

greater harmonisation in policy and service provisioning across these countries, in compliance with EOSC agreed standards and practices.

The project started in September 2019 and will end in August 2022. SND participates in two Work packages: *FAIR Data*, and *Open Research Data and Services – Demonstrators*.

[SSHOC \(Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud\)](#) is a cluster project to create an open cloud ecosystem for social sciences and humanities. The objective is to create a common European platform, where data, tools, and training resources are gathered in one place. SSHOC is one of five EU funded cluster projects that will run from 2019 through 2022. The project is a collaboration between 47 European organisations, coordinated by CESSDA. The results will be integrated in the larger EOSC platform.

SND participates in two tasks, *Data and Metadata Interoperability Hub* and *Certification Plan for SSHOC Repositories*.

[SEADDA \(Saving European Archeology from the Digital Dark Age\)](#) is a Cost Action project that will bring together an interdisciplinary network of archaeologists and computer scientists. There is a will to make archaeological data open and freely accessible, but the domain lacks appropriate, persistent repositories. To avoid losing generations of valuable research data, the project will create publications and materials that will set a state-of-the-art standard for archaeological archiving across Europe.

SEADDA started in April 2019 and runs until March 2023. SND participates as a Steering group member/Management committee member and up until September 2021 as Vice Chair in the working group *Stewardship of Archaeological Data*.

New Projects

During the year it was also decided that SND will participate in one of the Science Projects, *Climate Neutral and Smart Cities*, in the [EOSC Future](#) project. Preparations for the work to demonstrate that relevant environmental data and data on citizens' values, attitudes, behaviours and involvement can be combined for social, political and scientific analysis, started in the autumn of 2021.

Together with 43 other stakeholders, SND applied for EU funding for the pan-European Skills4EOSC (Skills for the European Open Science Commons) project. In the beginning of 2022, it was announced that funding for the project had been granted. Other Swedish participants are Chalmers University of Technology, Karolinska Institutet, and Umeå University.

Statistics

The SND research data catalogue has 1,740 searchable studies from a variety of research areas. In 2021, 100 new posts were added.

Users

SND has 1,919 registered users. There were 621 new registered users in 2021.

Catalogue Page Views

There were 53,560 views (or 44,528 unique views) of catalogue pages during 2021.

Downloaded Material

Many studies in the SND catalogue are freely accessible to download. There were 19,938 direct downloads* from the SND website in 2021.

Data Requests

Many studies that are not available to download can be requested from the SND catalogue. In 2021 SND received 481 requests, resulting in the dissemination of 2,644 studies.

Collections

Studies that form part of a collection or series are among the most popular requests. The two series with the greatest number of data requests in 2021 were the National Society Opinion Media (SOM) surveys and the Swedish National Election Studies. The SVT Exit Poll Surveys and the Media Barometer were also popular.

19,938 direct
downloads*

+100

catalogue
posts

53,560 views
(or 44,528 unique views)
of catalogue pages

+621

new users

* Total number of file downloads. Some datasets are comprised of several files. Attempts have been made to identify and remove automatic downloads by, for example, bots. It is however unlikely that they have been eliminated completely from the statistics.

Top 3 Downloads

- 1 Differences in metabolic profiles between the Burmese, the Maine Coon and the Birman cat - three breeds with varying risk for diabetes mellitus - **860 downloads**
- 2 Snow ice particle microphysical properties and fall speed from particle images taken in Kiruna (Sweden) 2014–2018 - **809 downloads**
- 3 The DREAM Dataset: Behavioural data from robot enhanced therapies for children with autism spectrum disorder - **764 downloads**

Top 3 Requested Collections

- 1 The National SOM survey - **1,382 requests**
- 2 Swedish Election Studies - Parliamentary elections - **495 requests**
- 3 SVT exit poll surveys - **143 requests**

Number of Catalogue Posts 1982–2021

Economy

SND ANNUAL ACCOUNTS 2021

Figures stated in thousand SEK

REVENUES	Notes	Results 2021	Budget 2021
Government Grants		7,000	7,000
Swedish Research Council, Core activities		13,000	13,000
Swedish Research Council, CESSDA activities		1,000	1,000
Other income – SND Network Services		1,690	1,875
Wage cost compensation from the Consortium		12,000	12,000
Other income – CESSDA Tasks		679	200
EU Project ARIADNEPlus		680	750
EU Project SSHOC		558	442
EU Project EOSC-Nordic		149	260
EU Project RDA		35	0
Other income		4	0
Total Revenues		36,795	36,527
EXPENSES			
Staff costs		-20,011	-21,526
Staff costs – Consortium		-12,000	-12,000
Rental of premises		-1,192	-1,174
Other operating costs		-140	-233
University IT fee, IT infrastructure, and IT licenses		-616	-726
Membership fees		-267	-421
University overhead and interest expense	1.	-2,755	-2,810
Depreciation		-25	-120
Internal co-financing CESSDA		-126	0
Scholarships for transfer		-30	0
Staff travel		-13	-300
Conference/course fees		-57	0
SND conferences	2.	0	-330
DoSp/Consortium activities	3.	-552	-800
Reversal	4.	-294	0
Total Expenses		-38,078	-40,440
RESULT		-1,283	-3,913
Opening balance 2021			6,660
Ending balance 2021			5,377

1. University overhead costs and negative interest for university bank funds.
2. Costs for Steering Group, Network activities and meetings.
3. Costs for DoSp Coordinator, Consortium activities and meetings.
4. Cancelling the prior year's accrual for RDA, which was far too highly estimated.

The ending balance shows an accumulated capital of 5.38 million SEK.

Staff

SND Gothenburg

Administration and Services

Director
Max Petzold

Administrator,
Language Coordinator
Lisa Isaksson

Communications
Officer
Matilda Lindmark

Communications
Officer
Helena Rohdén

Financial
Officer
Anna Maria Eriksson

Legal Officer
Erica Schweder

Senior Advisor
Iris Alfredsson

Senior Advisor
Birger Jerlehag

Repository and Training

Deputy Director,
Team Leader
Elisabeth Strandhagen

Domain Specialist in
the Humanities
Stefan Ekman

Research Data
Advisor
Anneli Ambring

Research Data
Advisor
Jeremy Azzopardi

Research Data
Advisor
Eira Brandby

Research Data
Advisor
Martin Brandhagen

Research Data
Advisor
Linda Härdelin

Research Data
Advisor
Ulf Jakobsson

Research Data
Advisor
Ilze Lace

Research Data
Advisor
Rufus Latham

Research Data
Advisor
Stephan Nylinder

Research Data
Advisor
Dimitar Popovski

Research Data
Advisor
Arin Savran

Research Data
Advisor
Sara Svensson

Research Data
Advisor
Sofia Österberg

Researcher
David Rayner

IT and Development

Head of IT
Johan Fihn Marberg

IT Architect
Olof Olsson

Substitute
IT Architect,
System Developer
Pablo Millet

System Developer
Alireza Davoudian

System Developer
Stefan Jakobsson

System Developer
Hasse Lans

System Developer
Joakim Larsson

System Developer
Tobias Linde

System Developer
Fabian Samuelsson

Without picture:

IT Technician, Alicia Olsbänning

Domain Specialists

Gustav Nilssonne
Coordinator
Karolinska Institutet

Anna Axmon
Lund University

Nicolo Dell'Unto
Lund University

Sudha Padmanabhan
MAX IV,
Lund University

Ulf Jansson
Stockholm University

Anders Moberg
Stockholm University

Cissi Jansson
Swedish University of
Agricultural Sciences

Ida Taberman
Swedish University of
Agricultural Sciences

Ylva Toljander
Swedish University of
Agricultural Sciences

Anders Brändström
Umeå University

Karina Nilsson
Umeå University

Marcus Lundberg
Uppsala University

Without picture:

Lars Eklund, Uppsala University

As well as Iris Alfredsson, Stefan Ekman and Elisabeth Strandhagen,
who are Domain Specialists at University of Gothenburg.

Steering Committee

Swedish National Data Service is run by a consortium consisting of nine universities. The steering committee of SND is made up of representatives from each of these universities. During 2021, the steering committee consisted of the following members:

Göran Landberg (Chair Jan–Aug)

Deputy vice-chancellor and professor, Institute of Biomedicine, University of Gothenburg

Carina Mallard (Chair Sep–Dec)

Deputy vice-chancellor and professor, Institute of Neuroscience and Physiology, University of Gothenburg

Ann-Sofie Axelsson

Head of department and library director, Chalmers University of Technology

Cecilia M. Björkdahl

Project leader at Grants Office, Karolinska Institutet

Lars Burman

Chief librarian, Uppsala University

Håkan Carlsson (June–Dec)

Library director, Lund University

Maria Haglund

Chief librarian, KTH Royal Institute of Technology

Monica Lassi (Jan–May)

IT Architect at LUNARC, Centre for Scientific and Technical Computing, Lund University

Urban Lindgren

Professor at Department of Geography, Umeå University

Astri Muren

Deputy vice-chancellor and professor, Department of Economics, Stockholm University

Linda Vidlund

Chief librarian, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences

